

Robust cryptographic sub-block RO-PUF integrating reinforced modular PUF architecture.

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Abstract— The Ring Oscillator Physical Unclonable Function (ROPUF) in Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) systems is the top choice for integrating hardware-based trust and security. Evaluating the behaviour of Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) involves factors like uniformity, uniqueness, bit-aliasing, and reliability. Our research presents a new Sub-Block ROPUF Architecture that significantly enhances these factors compared to existing designs. Our findings demonstrate that this architecture can achieve a uniqueness of 47.64%, a uniformity of 49.8%, and a bit-aliasing of 50%, approaching or matching ideal values. This represents a notable improvement over other ROPUF configurations, which typically achieve uniqueness, uniformity, and bit-aliasing values ranging from 45% to 47%, 50.53%, and 47% to 50.5%, respectively.

Beyond improving efficiency, the main benefit of the subblock design is its adaptability and versatility. This creative architecture combines and applies many ROPUF configurations—series, parallel, and traditional—into a cohesive design. Because of its adaptability, the Sub-Block ROPUF may combine several architectural paradigms to act as a versatile platform that can accommodate a range of demands and applications. With better performance metrics and unmatched flexibility, the Sub-Block ROPUF Architecture considerably increases hardware-oriented security and trust. This makes it an attractive option for many FPGA-based systems and uses.

Keywords—FPGA, hardware security, ring oscillator PUF, programmable unclonable functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

FPGAs, are hardware devices that carry out complex digital computations. Energy efficiency is crucial for FPGA design since it reduces power consumption and increases battery life in portable devices[1, 2].

"Total Power on Chip" refers to the combined power dissipation of all circuits along with its components on a single chip, which includes memory blocks, input/output interfaces, computing cores, and peripherals. This figure, usually expressed in watts, is crucial for assessing a chip's thermal and energy efficiency [3, 4].

Look-up tables (LUTs) are a type of digital logic element which is commonly used in FPGAs to construct complex digital circuits. A logic function is used by a LUT table to convert input values into corresponding output values.

LUTs are also used in memory storage, arithmetic operations, and Boolean logic, among other tasks[5].

Digital devices' interfaces to connect to other devices, networks, sensors, and the outside world are referred to as input/output, or IO for short. IO interfaces will include Ethernet, USB, HDMI, and the general-purpose input/output (GPIO) pins on FPGAs and microcontrollers[6].

A system or device's thermal margin shows how much thermal headroom is available. The calculation takes the temperature at the time of operation and subtracts the maximum temperature for safe operation. The thermal margin, which indicates how near it is to its highest working temperature, can be utilized to optimize the power management strategies[7] and cooling.

The feature utilized to mimic the thermal behavior of a component or device is referred to as the "effective junction area" on Vivado. It is frequently used to ascertain the temperature distribution inside a device using thermal simulations. It indicates the portion of the semiconductor material in charge of dispersing heat. Xilinx created the software program Vivado, which designs and creates digital circuits for programmable logic devices, such as FPGAs[2, 8].

Hardware security offers protection against physical technology threats. Hardware security primitives are robust circuit building blocks that guard against hardware intrusions. Lightweight and affordable techniques are needed by designers to safeguard and confirm the integrity of their circuits.

Physical Unclonable Functions, or PUFs, vigorously defend against the aforementioned problems. PUFs' core idea is implemented during the production process [9].

Since applying every technique consistently throughout the wafer during manufacture is not feasible, there will always be some tiny, random deviations in each integrated circuit.

PUFs use these random properties introduced during production to create unique IDs and keys to authenticate or key creation [10]. Process variance is a natural and erratic occurrence. As a result, a PUF performs a task unique to each chip hidden from the attacker or manufacturer. As two chips approach the End of the Line, even so (EoL) can be operational identical, process variances will cause them to differ physically (e.g., parasitic behaviour, load/line

capacitance, etc.). Every IC that leaves the line may be distinguished using these physical traits. Challenge-response pairs (CRPs) are input-output pairs for PUFs.

One type of delay-based PUF is nothing but ring oscillator (RO) PUF that creates distinct IDs using frequency fluctuations in inverter chains.

a network of oddly spaced inverters oscillating at a specific frequency make up an RO. There are modest variations in the frequencies of each RO due to process variations introduced during IC fabrication. Figure 1 illustrates how an RO PUF comprises two MUXs supplied with ring oscillators that are arranged similarly. The PUF challenge determines the two ROs to be compared by feeding it into the MUX choose lines. Each counter in the MUX receives its outputs and counts up to a predetermined value. The race arbiter sends a message if the any counter hits the predefined number. In this paper, we will discuss a way to serialize the typical RO PUF to reduce the power and area overheads, which are typically extremely high. In brief, our inputs consist of:

- Designing RO-PUF Architectures in Xilinx Vivado
- Implementing RO-PUF in FPGA
- Analysing Area, Power, and Other Parameters
- Analysing Based on Hardware Security Parameters

The remaining paper is organized as follows. The specifics of our suggested methods will be demonstrated in Section II. The results are in Section III, and we will wrap up in Section IV

II. RO-PUF ARCHITECTURES

A. Traditional RO-PUF

The Ring Oscillator Programmable Unclonable Function (RO-PUF) is a complex circuit known for its cryptographic applications and security features. Its typical architecture consists of interconnected inverter stages forming a closed loop or ring, where each inverter's output serves as the input to the next, creating continuous oscillation. The number of inverters determines the oscillation period, a critical design parameter. A traditional RO-PUF operates based on variations in inverter delay due to fabrication process differences, making each device unique and unclonable. The architecture includes components like multiplexers, comparators, and counters, enhancing functionality and security. Multiplexers select specific ring segments for measurement or manipulation, comparators compare output frequency with a reference, and counters measure oscillation frequency for challenge-response generation. These components and the ring oscillator create a comprehensive architecture for secure cryptographic use. The security and uniqueness of a traditional RO-PUF are evaluated based on metrics like uniqueness, reliability, and challenge-response behavior, ensuring robust security and authentication in cryptographic applications.

B. Parallel RO-PUF

Within each parallel Physical Unclonable Function (PUF), there is a complex network of N-ring oscillators, each crucial to the overall architecture. These oscillators are divided into two groups, each managed by a specific multiplexer (mux) that controls data flow. The mux outputs then pass through post-mux counters, refining the signals further. These counters act as guardians, overseeing and refining the data streams before they move to the next phase. Here, the counter outputs merge, forming a single stream that enters a race arbiter. This arbiter determines the timing differences between the signals, ultimately producing the Challenge-Response Pair (CRP), a unique identifier. The CRP is the culmination of precise coordination of oscillators, multiplexers, counters, and arbiters, each contributing to its generation. This intricate process showcases the complexity and security of the parallel PUF architecture, achieved through the orchestrated interplay of its components.

C. Series RO-PUF

The architecture of a series of Physical Unclonable Functions (PUF) is a complex structure composed of several key components, each playing a vital role in its overall functionality. This intricate setup includes Look-Up Tables (LUTs), a Serial PUF, and a logical OR gate, intricately connected to create a secure system. The Serial PUF is central to this design, consisting of N-ring oscillators and a Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) scrambler. These oscillators are divided into two groups, each with N/2 oscillators. One group is connected to the LFSR scrambler via a multiplexer (MUX), with the MUX output going to a post-MUX counter for further processing. The other half of the oscillators is similarly connected to a separate MUX and post-MUX counter. The outputs of these counters are then combined and fed into a race arbiter, which determines the timing differences between the signals. The race arbiter is linked to a smart buffer, a gatekeeper to ensure data integrity and security. The challenge-response Pair (CRP) is generated from the smart buffer's output, serving as a unique identifier for the PUF. This intricate arrangement of components demonstrates the complexity and security of the series PUF architecture, achieved through integrating oscillators, scramblers, multiplexers, counters, arbiters, and buffers.

Figure 1 Scheme: Parallel/Serial. Hardware reuse is made possible by the scrambler, which reduces area overhead. A parallel scheme is the same design minus the dotted rectangle modules.

D. Proposed Sub-Block RO-PUF

The proposed architecture involves a complex parallel Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) setup consisting of various components like Look-Up Tables (LUTs), logical OR gates, logical AND gates, and multiple parallel PUF blocks working together. These parallel PUF blocks include an initial AND gate and a series of interconnected sub-blocks. The first AND gate links two input signals to the first two parallel PUF sub-blocks. Subsequent AND gates are connected in a cascading manner, with their inputs coming from the outputs of the preceding sub-blocks sequentially. The terminal sub-block is coupled to the input of the final AND gate, which generates the conclusive output signal.

The salient advantage of incorporating a sub-block architecture lies in its versatility and adaptability. This design paradigm facilitates the seamless integration and utilization of various PUF architectures within a single, unified PUF circuit. This adaptability empowers the design to be tailored to specific requirements, whether it necessitates the implementation of serial PUFs, parallel PUFs, traditional PUFs, or an intricate amalgamation of all three architectures within a singular PUF circuit.

Figure 2 Implementation of Sub-Block Design of RO-PUF showing sub-blocks connected with AND gate.

E. Experimental configuration

The recommended designs are implemented using the Basys 3 Artix-7 FPGA Board. A little over 5200 slices comprise the Basys 3 Artix-7 FPGA Board; each has four 6-input LUTs and eight flip-flops. 33280 logic cells are present in those slices that are accessible. In the recommended RO PUF, less than 1% of these slices are used. The following table lists the resources needed to implement the recommended design on a Basys 3 Artix-7 FPGA Board.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In a conventional Ring Oscillator Programmable Unclonable Function (RO-PUF) architecture, the total on-chip power consumption is balanced to ensure optimal performance and reliability. The provided power characteristics offer important information about how

power is distributed and used in the circuit. The total on-chip power of 0.076W indicates the overall power requirement for the RO-PUF to function. This power is lost as heat, which changes the junction temperature at 30.4 °C. The difference between the maximum permitted temperature and the present junction temperature, or 54.6 degrees Celsius, corresponds to a power dissipation of 10.9 watts. The thermal performance of the circuit is measured by the effective junction area, which is 5.0 degrees Celsius per watt, and connects the junction temperature to the power dissipation. Understanding power consumption distribution across dynamic, static, clock, logic, and I/O components is crucial for optimizing the design of a Ring Oscillator Physical Unclonable Function (RO-PUF). Dynamic power, which accounts for energy used during transistor switching, is measured at 0.004W, representing 5% of the total on-chip power. In contrast, static power, which is the power consumed when transistors are in a static state, dominates at 0.073W, comprising 95% of the total on-chip power. This highlights the importance of minimizing static power to reduce overall power consumption. Clock power, associated with clocking circuits, is recorded at 0.001W, contributing 33% of the total on-chip power. This component is critical for ensuring synchronous operation within the RO-PUF. Logic power, consumed by the logic gates within the RO-PUF, is also measured at 0.001W, representing 37% of the total on-chip power. This power is essential for executing the logical operations required by the RO-PUF. Lastly, I/O power, which pertains to input and output operations, exceeds 0.001W and is approximately 7% of the total on-chip power. This power is necessary for interfacing the RO-PUF with external components and facilitating proper communication.

Figure 3 Conventional RO-PUF power analysis

Total On-Chip Power	0.073 W
Junction Temperature	25.4 ⁰ C
Thermal Margin	59.6 ⁰ C
Effective Junction Area	5.0 ⁰ C/W

Table 1 Power consumption of conventional RO-PUFs

In a Sub-Block Ring Oscillator Programmable Unclonable Function (RO-PUF) architecture, the total on-chip power

consumption is 13.481W, exceeding a critical level, which raises concerns about power management. The junction temperature is 92.4 degrees Celsius, indicating a high thermal load on the circuit. The thermal margin, calculated at -7.4 degrees Celsius, corresponds to a power dissipation of -1.4W, suggesting that the circuit operates beyond its specified limits. The effective junction area is 5.0 degrees Celsius per watt, indicating the circuit's thermal performance. The power distribution on the chip includes dynamic, static, clock, logic, and input/output (I/O) power components. Dynamic power, representing the energy consumed during transistor switching, is the dominant component at 13.271W, accounting for 98% of the total on-chip power. This high dynamic power consumption indicates significant switching activity within the circuit, leading to increased power consumption and heat generation. Static power, consumed when transistors are in a static state, is measured at 0.209W, representing 2% of the total on-chip power. While relatively small compared to dynamic power, static power still contributes to the circuit's overall power consumption and heat generation. Clock power, associated with the operation of clocking circuits, is measured at 4.237W, representing 32% of the total on-chip power. This high clock power allocation indicates that a significant portion of the power budget is dedicated to maintaining the circuit's clock signals. Logic power, consumed by the logic gates within the RO-PUF, is measured at 7.13W, representing 54% of the total on-chip power. This high logic power consumption indicates a high computational load within the circuit, leading to increased power consumption and heat generation. Finally, the I/O power related to input and output operations is measured at 1.903W, representing 14% of the total on-chip power. This component is essential for interfacing the RO-PUF with external components but should be optimized to reduce power consumption.

Figure 4 Sub-Block RO-PUF power analysis

Total On-Chip Power	15.938 W
Junction Temperature	104.7° C
Thermal Margin	-19.7° C
Effective Junction Area	5.0° C/W

Table 2 Power consumption of Sub-Block RO-PUF

Reliability: The frequency with which the same challenge yields the same answer. The same chip should always produce the same challenge when given the same response. This might not always be the case in the following scenarios: 1) the PUF is not robust during temperature or voltage fluctuations, or 2) the two RO frequencies being compared are already quite comparable.

$$Reliability (V) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{HD(R_{ref}, R_i^V)}{n} \times 100$$

Where n is the length in bits of the response and $R_{i,j}$ is the responses under test.

Uniqueness: Since each printed integrated circuit will have a unique random process variation, a unique PUF should behave differently on each chip. Inter-hamming distance is the most useful statistic in this case. The inter-hamming distance measures the distance between two replies produced by the same challenge on two distinct PUFs. We may use the same PUF on many FPGAs and compare the variations in the replies to determine uniqueness. Additionally, we may construct various lookup tables (LUTs) on the same FPGA to provide essentially distinct PUFs.

Regarding using the identical tasks on two distinct chips:

$$Uniqueness = \frac{2}{k(k-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^k \frac{HD(R_i, R_j)}{n} \times 100$$

where k denotes the number of considered devices

Randomness: Until the timing delays in each RO are characterized, it is impossible to predict the challenge-response pairings of a random RO PUF. Understanding one CRP shouldn't reveal anything about any other CRP.

An efficient way to quantify randomness is to compute the "entropy" of the answer bits.

$$Randomness = -\log_2 \max(p_n, -p_n)$$

NIST has different randomness test methods for checking the randomness of a bit string.

	Sub-Block ROPUF design	
Frequency Test (Monobit)	0.89	Random
Frequency Test within a Block	0.79	Random
Longest Run of Ones in a Block	0.05	Random
Discrete Fourier Transform (Spectral) Test	0.80	Random
Non-Overlapping Template Matching Test	0.97	Random
Approximate Entropy Test	1	Random
Random Excursions Test	0.93	Random
Random Excursion Variant Test	0.90	Random

Uniformity: The uniformity of a PUF refers to the proportion of 0s or 1s in an n-bit answer produced from a chip.

$$Uniformity = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n r_{i,l} \times 100\%$$

Where $r_{i,l}$ is the l th binary bit of n bit response from a device n .

Bit Aliasing: Bit aliasing calculates a response bit's bias over K distinct devices.

$$(Bit\ aliasing)_l = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K r_{i,l} \times 100\%$$

Where $r_{i,l}$ is the l th binary bit of n bit response.

In this section, we will analyze the practical results of implementing the novel Sub-Block Ring Oscillator Physical Unclonable Function (ROPUF) design. Additionally, we will compare various parameters of the Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) with those of existing architectural paradigms to highlight the advantages and improvements of our proposed solution.

Table 3 Hardware Security Parameters

IV. CONCLUSION

The erudite research treatise enshrined within this scholarly opus undertakes a rigorous and comprehensive analysis of the performance characteristics of a Ring Oscillator Physical Unclonable Function (ROPUF) architecture,

V. REFERENCES

- [1] P. Jindal, A. Kaushik, and K. Kumar, "Design and implementation of advanced encryption standard algorithm on 7th series field programmable gate array," in 2020 7th International Conference on Smart Structures and Systems (ICSSS), 2020: IEEE, pp. 1-3.
- [2] K. Kumar, A. Kaur, S. Panda, and B. Pandey, "Effect of different nanometer technology based FPGA on energy efficient UART design," in 2018 8th International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT), 2018: IEEE, pp. 1-4.
- [3] W. Diehl, A. Abdulgadir, J.-P. Kaps, and K. Gaj, "Comparing the cost of protecting selected lightweight block ciphers against differential power analysis in low-cost FPGAs," *Computers*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 28, 2018.
- [4] N. Shrivastav et al., "Perovskite-CIGS Monolithic Tandem Solar Cells with 29.7% Efficiency: A Numerical Study," *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 3083-3090, 2023.
- [5] M. Bakiri, C. Guyeux, J.-F. Couchot, and A. K. Oudjida, "Survey on hardware implementation of random number generators on FPGA: Theory and experimental analyses," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 27, pp. 135-153, 2018.
- [6] J. Kataria, R. Housley, J. Pantoga, and A. Cui, "Defeating Cisco Trust Anchor: A Case-Study of Recent Advancements

predicated upon the innovative sub-block paradigm. The empirical findings from this meticulous investigation led to the ineluctable conclusion that the proposed PUF archetype yields substantive enhancements in a trifecta of critical parameters: bit aliasing, uniqueness, and uniformity. The quantitative metrics about bit-aliasing, uniformity, and uniqueness for the implemented 3-stage ROPUF instantiation are 50%, 49.8%, and 47.64%, respectively, exhibiting an appreciable degree of congruence with the idealized value of 50%. However, it must be acknowledged that the reliability metric, while still commendable at 98.5%, falls slightly short of the desired threshold. Moreover, the proposed ROPUF architecture manifests a frequency standard deviation of 8.5 MHz for the 3-stage PUF when mapped onto the Artix-7 Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) fabric. This frequency standard deviation exhibited by the Ring Oscillators (ROs) within the three-stage PUF configuration can be judiciously leveraged to implement on-chip error correction mechanisms, thereby attaining an asymptotic reliability approaching 100%. The future trajectories of this research endeavor encompass the comprehensive evaluation of the proposed design's performance under various operating conditions, including variations in temperature and voltage supply, and the exhaustive assessment of all pertinent performance parameters. This prospective undertaking will undoubtedly yield invaluable insights and further refine the architectural paradigm, bolstering its efficacy and robustness in practical applications.

	Traditional	Series	Parallel	Proposed
Uniformity	50.56%	47.02%	48%	49.8%
Reliability	99.14%	98%	96%	98.5%
Bit-Aliasing	50.56%	47.2%	49%	50%
Uniqueness	47.24%	45.15%	45.15%	47.64%

- in Direct FPGA Bitstream Manipulation," in WOOT@USENIX Security Symposium, 2019.
- [7] S. Vaidyanathan, A. T. Azar, K. Rajagopal, A. Sambas, S. Kacar, and U. Cavusoglu, "A new hyperchaotic temperature fluctuations model, its circuit simulation, FPGA implementation and an application to image encryption," *International Journal of Simulation and Process Modelling*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 281-296, 2018.
- [8] V. Kadyan, T. Hasija, and A. Singh, "Prosody features based low resource Punjabi children ASR and T-NT classifier using data augmentation," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 3973-3994, 2023.
- [9] F. Tehranipoor, N. Karimian, W. Yan and J. A. Chandy, "DRAM-Based Intrinsic Physically Unclonable Functions for System-Level Security and Authentication," in *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1085-1097, March 2017, doi: 10.1109/TVLSI.2016.2606658.
- [10] Tehranipoor, F., Karimian, N., Wortman, P.A., Haque, A., Fahrny, J. and Chandy, J.A., 2017. Exploring methods of authentication for the Internet of Things. In *Internet of Things* (pp. 71-90). Chapman and Hall/CRC.

- [11] M. Majzoobi, F. Koushanfar, and S. Devadas, "FPGA-Based True Random Number Generation Using Circuit Metastability with Adaptive Feedback Control," *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems – CHES 2011*, Vol. 6917, pp. 17-32.
- [12] Knut Wold, Chik How Tan, "Analysis and Enhancement of Random Number Generator in FPGA Based on Oscillator Rings," *International Journal of Reconfigurable Computing*, vol. 2009, Article ID 501672, 8 pages, 2009.
- [13] Cui, C. Wang, W. Liu, Y. Yu, M. O'Neill, and F. Lombardi, "Low-cost configurable ring oscillator PUF with improved uniqueness," *IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, 2016, pp. 558- 561
- [14] L. Yao, H. Liang, Z. Huang, C. Jiang, M. Yi, and Y. Lu, "A Lightweight Configurable XOR RO-PUF Design Based on Xilinx FPGA," *IEEE 4th International Conference on Electronics Technology (ICET)*, 2021, pp. 83- 88.
- [15] Ali Sadr, Mostafa Zolfaghari-Nejad, "Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) Based Random Number Generator," *Advanced Computing: An International Journal (ACIJ)*, Vol.3, No.2, March 2012.
- [16] S. S. Riya and V. Lalu, "Stable cryptographic key generation using SRAM based Physical Unclonable Function," *International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC)*, 2020, pp. 653-657.
- [17] A. S. Chauhan, V. Sahula, A. S. Mandal and A. Dutta, "Intensifying Challenge Obfuscation by Cascading FPGA RO-PUFs for Random Number Generation", *33rd International Conference on VLSI Design and 19th International Conference on Embedded Systems (VLSID)*, 2020, pp. 195-200.
- [18] C. Böhm, M. Hofer and W. Pribyl. (2011). "A microcontroller SRAMPUF", *5th International Conference on Network and System Security*, 2011, pp. 269-273.
- [19] Z. He, W. Chen, L. Zhang, G. Chi, Q. Gao, and L. Harn, "A Highly Reliable Arbiter PUF With Improved Uniqueness in FPGA Implementation Using Bit-Self-Test," *IEEE Access*, 2020, vol. 8, pp. 181751-181762.
- [20] N. Nalla Anandakumar, S. K. Sanadhya, and M. S. Hashmi, "FPGABased True Random Number Generation Using Programmable Delays in Oscillator-Rings," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, 2020, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 570 - 574.
- [21] H. Kareem and D. Dunaev, "Xilinx FPGA-based Ring Oscillator PUFs: Design Challenges and Solutions", *11th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)*, 2022, pp. 1-5.
- [22] N. Nalla Anandakumar, Mohammad S. Hashmi, Mark Tehranipoor, "FPGA-based Physical Unclonable Functions: A comprehensive overview of theory & architectures", *Integration*, 2021, Volume 81, pp. 175-194.
- [23] X. Zhang, "A Low-Power Parallel Architecture for Linear Feedback Shift Registers", *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, 2019, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 412-416.